

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Convergent adaptation of true crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura) to a gradient of terrestrial environments

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Text S1. Supplemental methods.

Text S2. References associated with natural history codings in Table S5.

Figure S1. Gene tree for 12S. Nodes are unlabeled as gene trees were calculated as part of the concordance factor analysis (labels visualized in Figure S11). Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S2. Gene tree for 16S. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S3. Gene tree for 18S. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S4. Gene tree for 28S. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S5. Gene tree for AK. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S6. Gene tree for enolase. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S7. Gene tree for GADPH. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S8. Gene tree for H3. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S9. Gene tree for NaK. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S10. Gene tree for PEPCK. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S11. Full phylogenetic hypothesis for Brachyura based on the topology from the ML concatenated analysis. Values at nodes represent ultrafast bootstraps / gene concordance factors (gCF) by partition / updated site concordance factors (sCF). Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S12. Full phylogenetic hypothesis for Brachyura based on the topology from the Bayesian concatenated analysis. Values at nodes represent posterior probabilities. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S13. Plots of concordance factors versus UF bootstrap values for the ML concatenated tree. **(A)** Gene concordance factors by partition. **(B)** Updated site concordance factors.

Figure S14. Results of phylogenetic informativeness profiling for 10 Sanger genes.

Figure S15. Sensitivity of divergence time estimates to inference strategy plotted with *chronospace*, with outgroup taxa removed from these analyses. This plot shows between-group principal component analysis (bgPCA) separating chronograms by calibration strategy, for only relaxed lognormal clock models (all fully converged).

Figure S16. Full maximum clade credibility divergence time estimates for Brachyura as depicted in Figure 2. Posterior ages were estimated in BEAST2 using 36 vetted node calibrations (represented by numbered circles following the order in Text S1) and the topology fixed from Figure S11, a birth-death tree prior, and relaxed lognormal clock model. Horizontal shaded bars represent 95% HPD intervals. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S17. Full maximum clade credibility divergence time estimates for Brachyura using the FBD. Posterior ages were estimated in BEAST2 using 328 calibrations from PBDB added as rogues to the topology fixed from Figure S11, an FBD tree prior, and relaxed lognormal clock model. Horizontal shaded bars represent 95% HPD intervals. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S18. Full maximum clade credibility divergence time estimates for Brachyura using BDSS. Posterior ages were estimated in BEAST2 using 328 calibrations from PBDB added as rogues to the topology fixed from Figure S11, a BDSS tree prior, and relaxed lognormal clock model. Horizontal shaded bars represent 95% HPD intervals. Branches colored by superfamily, as for Figure 2.

Figure S19. Comparison of posterior probability distributions for divergence time analyses under different calibration strategies in BEAST2, and the same analyses under the marginal prior (removing sequence data). The posterior analyses are shaded; marginal priors are superimposed on the same axes with a heavy line of the same color. **(A)** Root; **(B)** 19 most sensitive nodes, calculated based on Figure 3A.

Figure S20. Inferred posterior birth rate through time, from BDSS analysis.

Figure S21. Summary of 500 stochastic character maps coding tips in a simplified form as: fully marine, terrestrial (through direct marine pathway), and freshwater, under the best-fitting all rates different (ARD) model. These codings are based on the transition pathways scored from the literature supported data in Table S5.

Figure S22. Ancestral state reconstruction for the sequence from fully marine to terrestrial through direct marine pathway, under the best-fitting OU model in *ancThresh*. The tip codings are based on estimates by family as coded in Table S6, with their prior probabilities visualized as small pies at tips.

Figure S23. Posterior density of liabilities estimated in *ancThresh*, indicating the thresholds of change required to shift character states. As in Sallan et al. (2018), the threshold for exiting marine (grade 0) is held at 0, and values for exiting grade 5 are infinity as there are no subsequent states to transition into. **(A)** Sequence from fully marine to terrestrial through direct marine pathway, under OU model, and **(B)** Sequence from fully marine to terrestrial through indirect freshwater pathway, under OU model.

Figure S24. Ancestral state reconstruction for the sequence from fully marine to terrestrial through indirect freshwater pathway, under the best-fitting OU model in *ancThresh*. The tip codings are based on estimates by family as coded in Table S6, with their prior probabilities visualized as small pies at tips.

Figure S25. Ancestral state reconstructions for transitions between pathways for subclade Hymenosomatidae, under the OU model in *ancThresh*. **(A)** From ancestrally freshwater to direct pathway. In this case, state 0 reflects fully marine plus terrestrial prior probabilities. **(B)** From terrestrial through the direct pathway, to freshwater. Posterior density of liabilities from **(C)** ancestrally freshwater to direct pathway and **(D)** terrestrial through the direct pathway, to freshwater.

Figure S26. Ancestral state reconstructions for transitions between pathways for subclade Sesamidae, under the OU model in *ancThresh*. **(A)** From ancestrally terrestrial to indirect freshwater pathway. In this case, state 0 reflects fully marine plus terrestrial prior probabilities. **(B)** From freshwater through the indirect pathway, to terrestrial. Posterior density of liabilities from **(C)** ancestrally terrestrial to indirect freshwater pathway and **(D)** freshwater through the indirect pathway, to terrestrial.

Table S1. Description of the pathways, grades, and characteristic traits of terrestriality, following Watson-Zink (2021).

Table S2. Sample information for new and previous sequence data.

Table S3. Fossil node calibrations with details following Wolfe et al. (2016, 2019) and elaborated in Luque et al. (2023). The topology defining the nodes is the concatenated ML tree.

Table S4. Properties of the 10% subsample of fossil occurrences from PBDB, ordered by age.

Table S5. Discrete coded terrestriality grades for all sequenced taxa, with evidence for each trait supported by literature. Transition pathway 0 represents fully marine lifestyle, 1 represents transition to terrestriality through marine pathway, 2 represents transition through freshwater pathway. Grades as in Watson-Zink (2021) and Table S1.

Table S6. Prior probabilities of terrestriality grades estimated for each family, accounting for states from taxa that are not sequenced, based on WoRMS. Transition pathway 0 represents fully marine lifestyle, 1 represents transition to terrestriality through marine pathway, 2 represents transition through freshwater pathway. Grades as in Watson-Zink (2021) and Table S1.

Table S7. Taxonomic key for line drawings in Figures 2 and 4.

Table S8. Model parameters estimated by *ancThresh*. Means reported for best-fitting model only (or OU model only for subclades), after excluding 20% burnin. As in Sallan et al. (2018), the threshold for exiting marine (grade 0) is held at 0, and values for exiting grade 5 are infinity as there are no subsequent states to transition into.

Text S1. Supplemental Methods

Taxon sampling

This dataset represents over 15 years of sampling crabs in the field or from museum collections (**Table S2**). The final dataset includes 88 families, 263 genera, 333 species and 338 individuals within the infraorder Brachyura, as well as six outgroups for a total of 344 tips, 45% representing new sequence data, with the remainder obtained directly from GenBank (**Table S2**). All taxonomy was checked against expert compilations (Ng et al. 2008; Poore and Ahyong 2023, WoRMS 2022).

Gene selection

A total of 10 genes were selected based on previous phylogenetic research of decapods (Spears and Abele 1998; Schubart et al. 2000; Tsang et al. 2008; Bracken-Grissom et al. 2013; Tsang et al. 2014). These included two mitochondrial ribosomal RNA (rRNA) coding genes, 12S (small ribosomal subunit) and 16S (large ribosomal subunit) as well as two nuclear rRNA genes, 18S (small ribosomal subunit) and 28S (large ribosomal subunit). The six nuclear protein-coding genes NaK (sodium–potassium ATPase α -subunit), PEPCK (phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase), GADPH (glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase), H3 (histone 3), enolase (phosphopyruvate hydratase), and AK (arginine kinase) were also included. A minimum of two genes were required for each taxon included in the analysis, with an average of seven genes available per tip.

DNA extraction, PCR, and sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from the gills, abdomen, pereopod, or pleopod, using the Qiagen DNeasy® Blood and Tissue Kit (Cat. No. 69582), QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Cat. No. 51304) or QIAamp DNA Micro Kit (Cat. No. 56304). Gene regions were amplified with polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using one or more sets of primers. Annealing temperatures and primer sequences are as follows: 12S rRNA (325 bp, Buhay et al. 2007), 16S rRNA (339 bp, Simon et al. 1994; Crandall and Fitzpatrick 1996; Schubart et al. 2002), 18S rRNA (1798 bp, Medlin et al. 1988; Whiting et al. 1997; Whiting 2002; Bracken et al. 2009), 28S rRNA (1892 bp, Whiting et al. 1997; Whiting 2002; Palero et al. 2008), histone 3 (H3) (336 bp, Colgan et al. 1998), NaK (606 bp, Tsang et al. 2008), PEPCK (582 bp, Tsang et al. 2008), GADPH (609 bp, Tsang et al. 2011), enolase (399 bp, Tsang et al. 2011), and AK (630 bp, Tsang et al. 2011).

PCR amplifications were performed in 25–50 μ l volumes containing 1 U of Taq polymerase (HotMaster, AccuPrime or REDTaq), PCR Buffer, 2.5 mM of deoxyribonucleotide triphosphate mix (dNTPs), 0.5 μ M forward and reverse primer, and 30–100 ng extracted DNA. The thermal profile used an initial denaturation for 1 min at 94°C followed by 30–40 cycles of 30 sec-1 min at 94°C, 45 sec-1 min at 46-58°C (depending on gene region), 1 min at 72°C and a final extension of 7 min at 72°C. PCR products were purified using filters (PrepEase™ PCR Purification 96-well Plate Kit, USB Corporation) and sequenced with ABI BigDye® terminator mix (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Cycle Sequencing reactions were performed in an Applied Biosystems 9800 Fast Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA), and sequencing products were run (forward and reverse) on an ABI 3730xl DNA Analyzer 96-capillary automated sequencer.

Phylogenetic analysis

Sequences (n = 2251) were assembled and trimmed within Geneious Prime (Kearse et al. 2012). All protein coding genes (AK, enolase, GADPH, H3, NaK, PEPCK) were checked for pseudogenes following Song et al. (2008). Ribosomal RNA genes (12S, 16S, 18S, 28S), were individually aligned using the MAFFT via local iterative refinement algorithms in Geneious v.2021.0.1 (Kearse et al. 2012; Katoh and Standley 2013). Protein-coding genes were individually aligned in Geneious using the MAFFT global iterative refinement algorithm. To remove regions of questionable homology, rRNA alignments were masked in GBlocks v.0.91b (Castresana 2000) under “less stringent” parameters.

Alignments were concatenated in Geneious Prime. Best-fitting partitions were selected by an edge-linked proportional model (Chernomor et al. 2016) and substitution models with ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) in IQ-TREE v.2.1.2 (Minh et al. 2020b). The best-fitting scheme was used to estimate the concatenated maximum likelihood (ML) phylogeny, also in IQ-TREE, using 10 independent runs with perturbation strength 0.2 and stopping at 500 iterations, selecting the best topology by the highest log likelihood (Zhou et al. 2018). Ultrafast (UF) bootstrap values were calculated from 1000 replicates using the -bnni flag (Hoang et al. 2018). Gene and site concordance factors (gCF and sCF, respectively) were calculated in IQ-TREE v.2.2.2 (Minh et al. 2020a; Mo et al. 2022), simultaneously generating individual gene trees using ML. We further explored the resolution of individual loci evolving at different rates by using a metric for per-site phylogenetic informativeness (Townsend 2007) estimated by the online PhyDesign program (<http://phydesign.townsend.yale.edu/>; López-Giráldez and Townsend 2011) using the DNArates substitution model.

We conducted a Bayesian inference (BI) analysis of the concatenated loci using MrBayes v.3.2.7 (Ronquist et al. 2012). Two runs (analyses starting from different start trees) and four chains (three heated and one cold per run) were run for 35 million generations with 25% burnin. Convergence was assessed by reaching effective sample size >200 for every parameter, and by evaluating posterior distributions in Tracer v.1.7.1 (Rambaut et al. 2018).

Fossil calibration and divergence time inference

We compared two strategies for fossil calibration: (1) 36 newly vetted node calibrations (Luque et al. 2023), and (2) 328 fossil occurrences from the Paleobiology Database (PBDB; <http://paleobiodb.org/>). For node calibration, all calibrations followed best practices regarding specimen data, morphological diagnosis, and stratigraphy (Parham et al. 2012; Wolfe et al. 2016; details in **Table S3** and Luque et al. 2023), and were assigned to a crown group node at the family level or higher. All internal calibration age distributions were uniform. We applied a root prior with a fossil-informed lognormal distribution (mean = 282 Ma, standard deviation = 0.25, offset = 25; based on the same node in Wolfe et al. [2019]). This node dating strategy used a birth-death tree prior.

We downloaded fossil occurrences from the PBDB on March 23, 2022, for Brachyura at family-level taxonomic resolution, excluding uncertain genera and species, with accepted names only, from Jurassic to Pleistocene. Issues are known with the entry of decapod fossil taxonomy in the PBDB, primarily with typos falsely creating multiple taxa for different occurrences that should belong to the same taxon (M. Uhen and M. Clapham, pers. comm.). Our efforts to

improve the accuracy of PBDB data included: spot checking occurrences, resolving all family level taxonomy (wherever we found errors) in the full sample of brachyuran occurrences, resolving genera in the subsampled occurrences (see below), and manually removing from our downloads 30 families that could not be placed in our tree (extant families without molecular data, or extinct families with no known phylogenetic context). We randomly subsampled 10% of the 3,276 remaining occurrences, resulting in a computationally tractable 328 occurrences. The subsample was a reasonable sample of ages (including the oldest possible age, at 201.3-145 Ma), represented 69% of fossil families, and slightly overrepresented non-marine paleoenvironments (details in **Table S4**). All fossil occurrences were assigned age ranges from the PBDB, each with a uniform distribution (Barido-Sottani et al. 2019, 2020). To incorporate these fossil samples as part of the inferred evolutionary process, we used the unresolved time-homogeneous fossilized birth-death (FBD) tree prior (Stadler 2010; Heath et al. 2014; O'Reilly and Donoghue 2020), conditioned on the same root prior as above. The diversification rate was assigned a uniform prior (0, infinity) to reflect the unknown proportion of extinct relative to extant species, and an initial rate of 0.01. The turnover rate and sampling proportion were both assigned uniform priors with distribution (0, 1). For rho, the proportion of living species sampled, the value was fixed at 0.04 based on 7,636 valid brachyuran species in WoRMS (WoRMS 2021).

To reflect the complete absence of brachyuran fossils from earlier than the Jurassic, which represents a known ghost lineage when compared to the diversity and abundance of outgroup anomuran fossils, thus earlier diversification of the sister group (Hegna et al. 2020; Wolfe et al. 2021), we also analyzed the fossil occurrence calibration set using a birth-death skyline tree prior with sequential sampling (BDSS; Stadler et al. 2013; Culshaw et al. 2019). Fossil sampling proportion was modeled as time-heterogeneous with time slices before and after the oldest fossil sample (initial values of 0 and 0.1, respectively), and a uniform prior distribution (0, 1). This was done using the TreeSlicer function from the *skylinetools* package (<https://github.com/laduplessis/skylinetools>). While we used the same root prior, the origin time was estimated with a uniform prior (182, 372) and an initial value of 325 Ma (Wolfe et al. 2019). The reproductive number R_0 (i.e., birth rate/total death rate) had a dimension of 5; this parameter and the total death rate were both assigned lognormal prior distributions.

All divergence time analyses were conducted in BEAST2 v.2.6.7 (Bouckaert et al. 2019) using a fixed starting tree derived from our ML concatenated results. When using fossil occurrences (FBD and BDSS analyses only), these were added to the starting tree as “rogues” (able to move within pre-assigned family level constraints following Barido-Sottani et al. [2022], as most decapod fossils are fragmentary and cannot be confidently assigned). All analyses linked the substitution models selected by ModelFinder, and the clock models of those partitions (4 categories total). For each calibration strategy and tree prior, we compared two clock models: relaxed lognormal (Drummond et al. 2006) and random local (Drummond and Suchard 2010), using lognormal priors on the mean branch rates (lower and upper values of 0.001 and 1, respectively). Analyses used four to six independent runs for at least 450 million generations with 25% burnin, visualized as a maximum clade credibility tree. Convergence was assessed as above. Having explored a total of six divergence time analyses, we visualized the results from different parameter sets using *chronospace* scripts (Mongiardino Koch et al. 2022), which provide a multidimensional representation of inferred node ages that can be broken down by different factors and models.

Ancestral state reconstruction

To code character states representing a gradient of terrestriality, we used a modified version of the trait-by-environment associations defined by Watson-Zink (2021), additional details in **Table S1**. Distinct transition pathways were defined for marine and freshwater routes. For each pathway, we used five of the six grades of increasing terrestriality; the highest level does not appear in our data (Watson-Zink 2021). We added a grade 0, to indicate that the ancestral state for all crabs is fully marine (**Fig. 1a-e**). Using this framework, we coded discrete grades of terrestriality following two schemes. The first scheme coded the taxa that were sequenced in our molecular phylogeny and required detailed justification from natural history literature (**Table S5, Text S2**). Justifications accounted for available data on adult habitat, osmoregulatory status, larval developmental strategy, primary respiratory structure, water-wicking setae, burrow type, and diurnal activity period (Watson-Zink 2021). As our phylogeny sampled 4% of brachyuran species as tips, we also constructed a scheme to estimate grades for unsampled species for which the phylogenetic positions are unknown. For this scheme, we downloaded all taxonomic data, including non-marine taxa, from WoRMS as of June 8, 2021. For families sampled in our tree, we used the WoRMS data to estimate the number of species that fall into each grade (without detailed literature survey per species) and accordingly assigned prior distributions to each tip on the molecular phylogeny (**Table S6**).

First, we used stochastic character mapping (Bollback 2006; Revell 2012) to infer ancestral states at each node on the chronogram with vetted calibrations. For this we used a single dataset, where the natural history codings were simplified to marine, and marine/direct and freshwater/indirect transition paths (i.e., three unordered states of a single character), with the posterior distribution simulated 500 times. Next, we used Bayesian threshold models (Felsenstein 2012; Revell 2014) to account for gradients of change. A character coded with discrete ordered states (i.e., our grades) was assumed to evolve according to an unobserved continuous trait called “liability” (here representing the coded natural history traits combined with additional unobserved factors). Following Sallan et al. (2018), we assume thresholds represent the amount of change in terrestriality traits that allows a habitat shift. As there are two independent transition pathways with their own gradients, these were analyzed separately for each pathway from marine to non-marine (and on subclades for transitions between direct and indirect pathways). Threshold models for ancestral state reconstruction were implemented as the *ancThresh* function in *phytools* (Revell 2012). Each *ancThresh* model (Brownian Motion: BM, Ornstein-Uhlenbeck: OU, and Pagel’s Lambda) was run for 50 million generations (5 million for subclades) with 20% burnin (Revell 2014; Sallan et al. 2018).

References

- Barido-Sottani J., Aguirre-Fernández G., Hopkins M.J., Stadler T., Warnock R.C. 2019. Ignoring stratigraphic age uncertainty leads to erroneous estimates of species divergence times under the fossilized birth-death process. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 286:20190685.
- Barido-Sottani J., Pohle A., De Baets K., Murdock D., Warnock R.C.M. 2022. Putting the F in FBD analyses: tree constraints or morphological data? *BioRxiv*.
- Barido-Sottani J., van Tiel N., Hopkins M.J., Wright D.F., Stadler T., Warnock R.C.M. 2020. Ignoring fossil age uncertainty leads to inaccurate topology and divergence times in time calibrated tree inference. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*. 8:183.
- Bollback J.P. 2006. SIMMAP: stochastic character mapping of discrete traits on phylogenies. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 7:88.
- Bouckaert R., Vaughan T.G., Barido-Sottani J., Duchêne S., Fourment M., Gavryushkina A., Heled J., Jones G., Kühnert D., De Maio N., Matschiner M., Mendes F.K., Müller N.F., Ogilvie H.A., du Plessis L., Poppinga A., Rambaut A., Rasmussen D., Siveroni I., Suchard M.A., Wu C.-H., Xie D., Zhang C., Stadler T., Drummond A.J. 2019. BEAST 2.5: An advanced software platform for Bayesian evolutionary analysis. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 15:e1006650.
- Bracken H.D., Toon A., Felder D.L., Martin J.W., Finley M., Rasmussen J., Palero F., Crandall K.A. 2009. The decapod tree of life: compiling the data and moving toward a consensus of decapod evolution. *Arthropod Systematics & Phylogeny*. 67:99–116.
- Bracken-Grissom H.D., Cannon M.E., Cabezas P., Feldmann R.M., Schweitzer C.E., Ah Yong S.T., Felder D.L., Lemaitre R., Crandall K.A. 2013. A comprehensive and integrative reconstruction of evolutionary history for Anomura (Crustacea: Decapoda). *BMC Evolutionary Biology*. 13:128.
- Buhay J.E., Moni G., Mann N., Crandall K.A. 2007. Molecular taxonomy in the dark: Evolutionary history, phylogeography, and diversity of cave crayfish in the subgenus *Aviticambarus*, genus *Cambarus*. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 42:435–448.
- Castresana J. 2000. Selection of conserved blocks from multiple alignments for their use in phylogenetic analysis. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 17:540–552.
- Chernomor O., von Haeseler A., Minh B.Q. 2016. Terrace aware data structure for phylogenomic inference from supermatrices. *Systematic Biology*. 6:997–1008.
- Colgan D.J., McLauchlan A., Wilson G.D.F., Livingston S.P., Edgecombe G.D., Macaranas J., Cassis G., Gray M.R. 1998. Histone H3 and U2 snRNA DNA sequences and arthropod molecular evolution. *Aust. J. Zool.* 46:419.
- Crandall K.A., Fitzpatrick J.F. 1996. Crayfish molecular systematics: Using a combination of procedures to estimate phylogeny. *Systematic Biology*. 45:1–26.
- Culshaw V., Stadler T., Sanmartín I. 2019. Exploring the power of Bayesian birth-death skyline models to detect mass extinction events from phylogenies with only extant taxa. *Evolution*. 73:1133–1150.
- Drummond A.J., Ho S.Y.W., Phillips M.J., Rambaut A. 2006. Relaxed phylogenetics and dating with confidence. *PLoS Biology*. 4:e88.
- Drummond A.J., Suchard M.A. 2010. Bayesian random local clocks, or one rate to rule them all. *BMC Biol*. 8:114.
- Felsenstein J. 2012. A comparative method for both discrete and continuous characters using the threshold model. *American Naturalist*. 179:145–156.
- Heath T.A., Huelsenbeck J.P., Stadler T. 2014. The fossilized birth-death process for coherent calibration of divergence-time estimates. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 111:E2957–E2966.
- Hegna T.A., Luque J., Wolfe J.M. 2020. The fossil record of the Pancrustacea. In: Poore G.C.B., Thiel M., editors. *Evolution and Biogeography*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. p. 21–52.
- Hoang D.T., Chernomor O., von Haeseler A., Minh B.Q., Vinh L.S. 2018. UFBoot2: Improving the ultrafast bootstrap approximation. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 35:518–522.
- Kalyaanamoorthy S., Minh B.Q., Wong T.K.F., von Haeseler A., Jermiin L.S. 2017. ModelFinder: fast model selection for accurate phylogenetic estimates. *Nature Methods*. 14:587–589.
- Katoh K., Standley D.M. 2013. MAFFT Multiple sequence alignment software version 7: Improvements in performance and usability. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 30:772–780.
- Kearse M., Moir R., Wilson A., Stones-Havas S., Cheung M., Sturrock S., Buxton S., Cooper A., Markowitz S., Duran C., Thierer T., Ashton B., Meintjes P., Drummond A. 2012. Geneious Basic: An integrated and extendable desktop software platform for the organization and analysis of sequence data. *Bioinformatics*. 28:1647–1649.

- López-Giráldez F., Townsend J.P. 2011. PhyDesign: an online application for profiling phylogenetic informativeness. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*. 11:152.
- Luque, J., Bracken-Grissom H.D., Ortega-Hernández J., Wolfe J.M. 2023. Fossil calibrations for molecular analyses and divergence time estimation for true crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura). *BioRxiv*.
- Medlin L., Elwood H.L., Stickel S., Sogin M.L. 1988. The characterization of enzymatically amplified eukaryotic 16S-like rRNA-coding regions. *Gene*. 71:491–499.
- Minh B.Q., Hahn M.W., Lanfear R. 2020a. New methods to calculate concordance factors for phylogenomic datasets. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 37:2727–2733.
- Minh B.Q., Schmidt H., Chernomor O., Schrempf D., Woodhams M., von Haeseler A., Lanfear R. 2020b. IQ-TREE 2: New models and efficient methods for phylogenetic inference in the genomic era. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 37:1530–1534.
- Mo Y.K., Lanfear R., Hahn M.W., Minh B.Q. 2022. Updated site concordance factors minimize effects of homoplasy and taxon sampling. *Bioinformatics*.:1–2.
- Mongiardino Koch N., Thompson J.R., Hatch A.S., McCowin M.F., Armstrong A.F., Coppard S.E., Aguilera F., Bronstein O., Kroh A., Mooi R., Rouse G.W. 2022. Phylogenomic analyses of echinoid diversification prompt a re-evaluation of their fossil record. *eLife*. 11:e72460.
- Ng P.L.K., Guinot D., Davie P.J.F. 2008. Systema Brachyurorum: Part I. An annotated checklist of extant brachyuran crabs of the world. *Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*. 17:1–286.
- O'Reilly J.E., Donoghue P.C.J. 2020. The effect of fossil sampling on the estimation of divergence times with the Fossilized Birth–Death process. *Systematic Biology*. 69:124–138.
- Palero F., Guerao G., Abello P. 2008. Morphology of the final stage phyllosoma larva of *Scyllarus pygmaeus* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Scyllaridae), identified by DNA analysis. *Journal of Plankton Research*. 30:483–488.
- Parham J.F., Donoghue P.C.J., Bell C.J., Calway T.D., Head J.J., Holroyd P.A., Inoue J.G., Irmis R.B., Joyce W.G., Ksepka D.T., Patane J.S.L., Smith N.D., Tarver J.E., van Tuinen M., Yang Z., Angielczyk K.D., Greenwood J.M., Hipsley C.A., Jacobs L., Makovicky P.J., Muller J., Smith K.T., Theodor J.M., Warnock R.C.M., Benton M.J. 2012. Best practices for justifying fossil calibrations. *Systematic Biology*. 61:346–359.
- Poore G.C.B., Ah Yong S.T. 2023. Marine decapod Crustacea: a guide to the families and genera of the world. CSIRO Publishing.
- Rambaut A., Drummond A.J., Xie D., Baele G., Suchard M.A. 2018. Posterior summarisation in Bayesian phylogenetics using Tracer 1.7. *Systematic Biology*. 67:901–904.
- Revell L.J. 2012. phytools: an R package for phylogenetic comparative biology (and other things). *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 3:217–223.
- Revell L.J. 2014. Ancestral character estimation under the threshold model from quantitative genetics. *Evolution*. 68:743–759.
- Ronquist F., Teslenko M., van der Mark P., Ayres D.L., Darling A., Höhna S., Larget B., Liu L., Suchard M.A., Huelsenbeck J.P. 2012. MrBayes 3.2: Efficient Bayesian phylogenetic inference and model choice across a large model space. *Systematic Biology*. 61:539–542.
- Sallan L., Friedman M., Sansom R.S., Bird C.M., Sansom I.J. 2018. The nearshore cradle of early vertebrate diversification. *Science*. 362:460–464.
- Schubart C.D., Cuesta J.A., Felder D.L. 2002. Glyptograpsidae, a new brachyuran family from Central America: Larval and adult morphology, and a molecular phylogeny of the Grapsoidae. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 22:28–44.
- Schubart C.D., Neigel J.E., Felder D.L. 2000. The use of the mitochondrial 16S rDNA gene for phylogenetics and biogeographic studies of Crustacea. *Crustacean Issues: The Biodiversity Crisis and Crustacea*. Boca Raton: CRC Press. p. 817–830.
- Simon C., Frati F., Beckenbach A., Crespi B., Liu H., Flook P. 1994. Evolution, weighting, and phylogenetic utility of mitochondrial gene sequences and a compilation of conserved Polymerase Chain Reaction primers. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*. 87:651–701.
- Song H., Buhay J.E., Whiting M.F., Crandall K.A. 2008. Many species in one: DNA barcoding overestimates the number of species when nuclear mitochondrial pseudogenes are coamplified. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 105:13486–13491.
- Spears T., Abele L.G. 1998. Crustacean phylogeny inferred from 18S rDNA. In: Fortey R.A., Thomas R.H., editors. *Arthropod Relationships*. Dordrecht: Springer. p. 169–187.
- Stadler T. 2010. Sampling-through-time in birth–death trees. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*. 267:396–404.

- Stadler T., Kuhnert D., Bonhoeffer S., Drummond A.J. 2013. Birth-death skyline plot reveals temporal changes of epidemic spread in HIV and hepatitis C virus (HCV). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 110:228–233.
- Townsend J.P. 2007. Profiling phylogenetic informativeness. *Systematic Biology*. 56:222–231.
- Tsang L.M., Chan T.-Y., Ah Yong S.T., Chu K.H. 2011. Hermit to king, or hermit to all: Multiple transitions to crab-like forms from hermit crab ancestors. *Systematic Biology*. 60:616–629.
- Tsang L.M., Ma K.Y., Ah Yong S.T., Chan T.-Y., Chu K.H. 2008. Phylogeny of Decapoda using two nuclear protein-coding genes: Origin and evolution of the Reptantia. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*. 48:359–368.
- Tsang L.M., Schubart C.D., Ah Yong S.T., Lai J.C.Y., Au E.Y.C., Chan T.-Y., Ng P.K.L., Chu K.H. 2014. Evolutionary history of true crabs (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) and the origin of freshwater crabs. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 31:1173–1187.
- Watson-Zink V.M. 2021. Making the grade: Physiological adaptations to terrestrial environments in decapod crabs. *Arthropod Structure & Development*. 64:101089.
- Whiting M.F. 2002. Mecoptera is paraphyletic: multiple genes and phylogeny of Mecoptera and Siphonaptera. *Zoologica Scripta*. 31:93–104.
- Whiting M.F., Carpenter J.C., Wheeler Q.D., Wheeler W.C. 1997. The Strepsiptera problem: Phylogeny of the holometabolous insect orders inferred from 18S and 28S ribosomal DNA sequences and morphology. *Systematic Biology*. 46:1–68.
- Wolfe J.M., Breinholt J.W., Crandall K.A., Lemmon A.R., Moriarty Lemmon E., Timm L.E., Siddall M.E., Bracken-Grissom H.D. 2019. A phylogenomic framework, evolutionary timeline, and genomic resources for comparative studies of decapod crustaceans. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*. 286:20190079.
- Wolfe J.M., Daley A.C., Legg D.A., Edgecombe G.D. 2016. Fossil calibrations for the arthropod Tree of Life. *Earth-Science Reviews*. 160:43–110.
- Wolfe J.M., Luque J., Bracken-Grissom H.D. 2021. How to become a crab: Phenotypic constraints on a recurring body plan. *BioEssays*. 43:2100020.
- WoRMS. 2021. Brachyura. Accessed at: <https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=106673> on 06-08-2021.
- WoRMS. 2022. Brachyura. Accessed at: <https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=106673> on 12-08-2022.
- Zhou X., Shen X.-X., Hittinger C.T., Rokas A. 2018. Evaluating fast Maximum Likelihood-based phylogenetic programs using empirical phylogenomic data sets. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*. 35:486–503.

Text S2. Natural History References

These are the references listed in Table S5.

- Aagaard A., Styrishave B., Warman C.G., Depledge M.H. 2000. The use of cardiac monitoring in the assessment of mercury toxicity in the subtropical pebble crab *Gaetice depressus* (Brachyura: Grapsidae: Varuninae). *Sci. Mar.* 64:381–386.
- Abele L.G. 1979. The community structure of coral-associated decapod crustaceans in variable environments. In: Livingston R.J., editor. *Ecological Processes in Coastal and Marine Systems*. Boston, MA: Springer US. p. 265–287.
- Adamczewska A.M., Morris S. 2000. Locomotion, respiratory physiology, and energetics of amphibious and terrestrial crabs. *Physiological and Biochemical Zoology*. 73:706–725.
- Agusto L.E., Fratini S., Jimenez P.J., Quadros A., Cannicci S. 2021. Structural characteristics of crab burrows in Hong Kong mangrove forests and their role in ecosystem engineering. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*. 248:106973.
- Al-Aidaros A.M., Al-Haj A.E., Kumar A.A.J. 2014. Complete larval development of the Brachyuran crab (*Epixanthus frontalis* H. Milne Edwards, 1834) (Crustacea, Decapoda, Eriphioidea, Oziidae) under laboratory conditions. *Zootaxa*. 3815:29.
- Arias-Pineda J.Y., Gómez D.A., Magalhães C. 2015a. Range extension of the genus *Fredilocarcinus* Pretzmann, 1978 (Crustacea: Decapoda: Trichodactylidae) to Colombia. *Checklist: The Journal of Biodiversity Data*. 11:1586.
- Augusto A., Greene L.J., Laure H.J., Mcnamara J.C. 2007. Adaptive shifts in osmoregulatory strategy and the invasion of freshwater by brachyuran crabs: evidence from *Dilocarcinus pagei* (Trichodactylidae). *J. Exp. Zool.* 307A:688–698.
- Banerjee S., Ramakrishnan S.C. 2022. The first record of *Ozius tuberculosus* H. Milne Edwards (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) from the East Coast of Indian subcontinent. *Research Square*.
- Barnes R.S.K. 1967. The osmotic behaviour of a number of grapsoid crabs with respect to their differential penetration of an estuarine system. *Journal of Experimental Biology*. 47:535–551.
- Barnwell F.H. 1968. The role of rhythmic systems in the adaptation of fiddler crabs to the intertidal zone. *Am Zool.* 8:569–583.
- Bello-González O.C., Wehrtmann I.S., Magalhães C. 2016. First confirmed report of a primary freshwater crab (Brachyura: Pseudothelphusidae) associated with bromeliads in the Neotropics. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 36:303–309.
- Bennett D.B. 1995. Factors in the life history of the edible crab (*Cancer pagurus* L.) that influence modelling and management. *ICES Mar. Sci. Symp.*, 199: 89-98.
- Bianchini A., Gilles R. 1996. Toxicity and accumulation of mercury in three species of crabs with different osmoregulatory capacities. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*. 57:91–98.
- Branch G.M., Grindley J.R. 1979. Ecology of southern African estuaries Part XI. Mngazana: a mangrove estuary in Transkei. *South African Journal of Zoology*. 14:149–170.
- Bright D.B., Hogue C.L. 1972. A synopsis of the burrowing land crabs of the world and list of their arthropod symbionts and burrow associates. *Contributions in Science*. 220:1–58.
- Brown S., Bert T. 1993. The effects of temperature and salinity on molting and survival of *Menippe adina* and *M. mercenaria* (Crustacea, Decapoda) postsettlement juveniles. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 99:41–49.
- Brown S.D., Bert T.M., Tweedale W.A., Torres J.J., Lindberg W.J. 1992. The effects of temperature and salinity on survival and development of early life stage Florida stone crabs *Menippe mercenaria* (Say). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. 157:115–136.
- Cannicci S., Ruwa R.K., Giuggioli M. 1998. Predatory activity and spatial strategies of *Epixanthus dentatus* (Decapoda: Oziidae), an ambush predator among the mangroves. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 18(1): 57-63.
- Charmantier G., Charmantier-Daures M. 1991. Ontogeny of osmoregulation and salinity tolerance in *Cancer irroratus*; elements of comparison with *C. borealis* (Crustacea, Decapoda). *The Biological Bulletin*. 180:125–134.
- Chen T.-Y., Hwang G.-W., Mayfield A.B., Chen C.-P., Lin H.-J. 2019. The development of habitat suitability models for fiddler crabs residing in subtropical tidal flats. *Ocean & Coastal Management*. 182:104931.

- Cieluch U., Anger K., Aujoulat F., Buchholz F., Charmantier-Daures M., Charmantier G. 2004. Ontogeny of osmoregulatory structures and functions in the green crab *Carcinus maenas* (Crustacea, Decapoda). *Journal of Experimental Biology*. 207:325–336.
- Clark P.F., Paula J. 2003. Descriptions of ten xanthoidean (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) first stage zoeas from Inhaca island, Mozambique. *Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*. 51:323–378.
- Cook B.D., Pringle C.M., Hughes J.M. 2008. Phylogeography of an island endemic, the Puerto Rican Freshwater Crab (*Epilobocera sinuatifrons*). *Journal of Heredity*. 99:157–164.
- Cuesta J.A., Guerao G., Liu H.-C., Schubart C.D. 2006. Morphology of the first zoeal stages of eleven Sesamidae (Crustacea, Brachyura, Thoracotremata) from the Indo-West Pacific, with a summary of familial larval characters. *Invertebrate Reproduction & Development*. 49:151–173.
- Cumberlidge N. 1991. The Respiratory System of *Globonantes macropus* (Rathbun, 1898), a terrestrial freshwater crab from Liberia (Gecarcinucoidea, Gecarcinucidae). *Crustac.* 61:69–80.
- Cumberlidge N. 2008. Insular species of Afrotropical freshwater crabs (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Potamonautidae and Potamidae) with special reference to Madagascar and the Seychelles. *Contributions to Zoology*. 77:71–81.
- Cumberlidge N. 2009. The status and distribution of freshwater crabs [West Africa]. In: *The Status and Distribution of Freshwater Biodiversity in Western Africa*. Compilers: Smith, K.G., Diop, M.D., Niane, M. and Darwall, W.R.T. IUCN & Wetlands International report. Gland, Switzerland and Cambridge, UK: pp56–72
- Curtis D.L., McGaw I.J. 2008. A year in the life of a Dungeness crab: methodology for determining microhabitat conditions experienced by large decapod crustaceans in estuaries. *Journal of Zoology*. 274:375–385.
- Davie P.J.F., Guinot D., Ng P.K.L. 2015. Anatomy and functional morphology of Brachyura. *Crustacea* 9C (71-2): 11-163.
- Kunsook C., Dumrongrojwathana P. 2017. Species diversity and abundance of marine crabs (Portunidae: Decapoda) from a collapsible crab trap fishery at Kung Krabaen Bay, Chanthaburi Province, Thailand. *Tropical Life Sciences Research*. 28:45–67.
- Depledge M.H. 1989. Observations on the feeding behaviour of *Gaetice depressus* (Grapsidae: Varuninae) with special reference to suspension feeding. *Marine Biology*. 100:253–259.
- Diamond D.W., Scott L.K., Forward R.B., Kirby-Smith W. 1989. Respiration and osmoregulation of the estuarine crab, *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* (Gould): Effects of the herbicide, Alachlor. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology*. 93:313–318.
- Dornelas M., Paula J., Macia A. 2003. The larval development of *Hymenosoma orbiculare* Desmarest, 1825 (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Hymenosomatidae). *Journal of Natural History*. 37:2579–2597.
- Edkins M.T., Teske P.R., Papadopoulos I., Griffiths C.L. 2007. Morphological and genetic analyses suggest that southern African crown crabs, *Hymenosoma orbiculare*, represent five distinct species. *Crustaceana*. 80:667–683.
- Edwards M. 1986. Bimodal respiration, water balance and acid-base regulation in a high-shore crab, *Cyclograpsus lavauxi* H. Milne Edwards. *J. Exp. Mar. Bio. Ecol.*, Vol. 100, pp. 127 - 145.
- Erkan M., Balkis H., Tunali Y., Oliveria E. 2009. Morphology of testis and vas deferens in the xanthoid crab, *Eriphia verrucosa* (Forskål, 1775) (Decapoda: Brachyura). *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 29:458–465.
- Eshky A., Atkinson R., Taylor A. 1995. Physiological ecology of crabs from Saudi Arabian mangrove. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 126:83–95.
- Esser L.J., Cumberlidge N. 2011. Evidence that salt water may not be a barrier to the dispersal of Asian freshwater crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura: Gecarcinucidae and Potamidae). *Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*, 59(2): 259–268.
- Fadlaoui S., Melhaoui M. 2019. Population structure of the freshwater crab *Potamon algeriense* (Bott, 1967) inhabiting Oued Zegzel, (Northeast of Morocco). *International Journal of Ecology*. 2019:1–7.
- Felder D.L., Martin J.W., Goy J.W. 2017. Patterns in early postlarval development of decapods. In: Schram F.R., Wenner A.M., editors. *Crustacean Issues* 2. Routledge. p. 163–225.
- Fernandes L.S., Sant'Anna B.S., Hattori G.Y. 2020. Amazon freshwater crab *Dilocarcinus pagei* (Decapoda: Trichodactylidae): a view about burrow construction behavior. *Lat. Am. J. Aquat. Res.* 48:85–93.
- Figueiredo J., Penha-Lopes G., Anto J., Narciso L., Lin J. 2008. Fecundity, brood loss and egg development through embryogenesis of *Armases cinereum* (Decapoda: Grapsidae). *Mar Biol.* 154:287–294.
- Farhadi A., Harlioglu M.M. 2018. Distribution and diversity of freshwater crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura: Potamidae, Gecarcinucidae) in Iranian inland waters. *Aquatic Sciences and Engineering*:110–116.
- Felder D.L., Rabalais N.N. 1986. The Genera *Chasmocarcinus* Rathbun and *Speocarcinus* Stimpson on the Continental Shelf of the Gulf of Mexico, with Descriptions of Two New Species (Decapoda: Brachyura: Goneplacidae). *Journal Of Crustacean Biology*. 6:30.

- Foale S. 1999. Local Ecological Knowledge and Biology of the Land Crab *Cardisoma hirtipes* (Decapoda: Gecarcinidae) at West Nggela, Solomon Islands. *Pacific Science*. 53:13.
- Forward R.B. 2009. Larval Biology of the Crab *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* (Gould): A Synthesis. *The Biological Bulletin*. 216:243–256.
- Fowler A., Forsström T., von Numers M., Vesakoski O. 2013. The North American mud crab *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* (Gould, 1841) in newly colonized Northern Baltic Sea: distribution and ecology. *Aquatic Invasions*. 8:89–96.
- Rodriguez G., Ng P.K.L. 1995. Freshwater Crabs as Poor Zoogeographical Indicators: A Critique of Bănărescu (1990). *Crustaceana*. 68:636–645.
- Fukui Y. 1988. Comparative Studies on the Life History of the Grapsid Crabs (Crustacea, Brachyura) Inhabiting Intertidal Cobble and Boulder Shores. *Publ. SMBL*. 33:121–162.
- Full R.J., II C.F.H., Assad J.A. 1985. Energetics of the Exercising Wharf Crab *Sesarma cinereum*. *Physiological Zoology*. 58:605–615.
- Galil B., Vannini M. 1990. Research on the coast of Somalia. Xanthidae Trapeziidae Carpiliidae Menippidae (Crustacea Brachyura). *Tropical Zoology*. 3:21–56.
- Giraldes B.W., Chatting M., Smyth D. 2019. The fishing behaviour of *Metopograpsus messor* (Decapoda: Grapsidae) and the use of pneumatophore-borne vibrations for prey-localizing in an arid mangrove setting. *J. Mar. Biol. Ass.* 99:1353–1361.
- Goodman S.H., Cavey M.J. 1990. Organization of a phyllobranchiate gill from the green shore crab *Carcinus maenas* (Crustacea, Decapoda). *Cell Tissue Res.* 260:495–505.
- Guerao G. 2004. Complete larval and early juvenile development of the mangrove crab *Perisesarma fasciatum* (Crustacea: Brachyura: Sesarmidae) from Singapore, with a larval comparison of *Parasesarma* and *Perisesarma*. *Journal of Plankton Research*. 26:1389–1408.
- Guinot D. 2007. A new genus of the family Plagusiidae Dana, 1851, close to *Plagusia* Latreille, 1804 (Crustacea, Decapoda, Brachyura). *Zootaxa*. 1498:27–33.
- Hartnoll R. 2009. Sexual Maturity and Reproductive Strategy of the Rock Crab *Grapsus adscensionis* (Osbeck, 1765) (Brachyura, Grapsidae) on Ascension Island. *Crustac.* 82:275–291.
- Hartnoll R.G. 1976. The ecology of some rocky shores in tropical East Africa. *Estuarine and Coastal Marine Science*. 4:1–21.
- Hegerl E.J., Davie J.D.S. 1970. The mangrove forests of Cairns, Northern Australia. *Mar. Res. Indonesia*. 18:23–57.
- Herreid C.F., Gifford C.A. 1963. The Burrow Habitat of the Land Crab, *Cardisoma guanhumi* (Latreille). *Ecology*. 44:773–775.
- Hill B.J., Forbes A.T. 1979. Biology of *Hymenosoma orbiculare* Desm in Lake Sibaya. *South African Journal of Zoology*. 14:75–79.
- Holsman K., McDonald P., Armstrong D. 2006. Intertidal migration and habitat use by subadult Dungeness crab *Cancer magister* in a NE Pacific estuary. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 308:183–195.
- Hsueh P.-W. 2018. A new species of *Neorhynchoplax* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Hymenosomatidae) from Taiwan. *Zootaxa*. 4461:350.
- Huang J.-F., Yang S.-L., Ng P.K.L. 1998. Notes On the Taxonomy and Distribution of Two Closely Related Species of Ghost Crabs, *Ocypode sinensis* and *O. cordimanus* (Decapoda, Brachyura, Ocypodidae). *Crustac.* 71:942–954.
- Hunter K.C., Rudy P.P. 1975. Osmotic and ionic regulation in the Dungeness crab, *Cancer magister* Dana. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology*. 51:439–447.
- Vázquez-López H., Vega-Villasante F., Rodríguez-Varela A.C., Cruz-Gómez A. 2014. Population density of the land crab *Cardisoma crassum* Smith, 1870 (Decapoda: Gecarcinidae) in the estuary El Salado, Puerto Vallarta, Jalisco, Mexico. *International Journal of Innovative and Applied Research*. 2:1-9.
- IUCN. 2008a. *Ceylonthelphusa alpina*: Bahir, M.M., Ng, P.K.L., Crandall, K. & Pethiyagoda, R. and Cumberlidge, N.: The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2008: e.T61690A12525900. .
- IUCN. 2008b. *Potamonautes perlatus*: Cumberlidge, N.: The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2008: e.T64389A12767481. .
- IUCN. 2018. *Syntripsa flavichela*: Schubart, C.: The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2018: e.T134942A109683110.
- Jones D.A. 1972. Aspects of the ecology and behaviour of *Ocypode ceratophthalmus* (Pallas) and *O. kuhlii* de Haan (Crustacea: Ocypodidae). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. 8:31–43.
- Kennish R., Williams G. 1997. Feeding preferences of the herbivorous crab *Grapsus albolineatus*: The differential influence of algal nutrient content and morphology. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 147:87–95.

- Kepel' A.A., Tsareva L.A. 2005. First Record of Tropical Crabs *Portunus sanguinolentus* (Herbst, 1783) and *Plagusia depressa tuberculata* Lamarck, 1818 in Peter the Great Bay, Sea of Japan. *Russ J Mar Biol.* 31:124–125.
- Kim S.Y., Yi C.H., Kim J.M., Choi W.Y., Kim H.S., Kim M.-S. 2020. DNA Barcoding of the Marine Protected Species *Parasesarma bidens* (Decapoda: Sesarmidea) from the Korean Waters. *Animal Systematics, Evolution and Diversity.* 36:159–163.
- Kitaura J., Wada K., Nishida M. 2002. Molecular phylogeny of grapsoid and ocy podoid crabs with special reference to the genera *Metaplax* and *Macrophthalmus*. *Journal Of Crustacean Biology.* 22:12.
- Kobayashi S., Archdale M.V. 2022. Burrow utilization by the Japanese mitten crab *Eriocheir japonica* in the clay sediment of a freshwater river of Kyushu, Japan. *Crust Res.* 51:17–29.
- Kobayashi S., Vazquez Archdale M. 2021. Habitat preference and locomotive traits of the Japanese mitten crab *Eriocheir japonica* within the stream unit of the freshwater river environment. *Limnologica.* 88:125870.
- Krediet C.J., Donahue M.J. 2009. Growth-mortality trade-offs along a depth gradient in *Cancer borealis*. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology.* 373:133–139.
- Krishnan T., Kannupandi T. 1988. Larval development of *Elamena (Trigonoplax) cimex* Kemp, 1915 in the laboratory: The most unusual larvae known in the Brachyura (Crustacea: Decapoda). *Bulletin Of Marine Science.* 43:14.
- Krishnan T., Kannupandi T. 1989. Laboratory cultured zoeae and megalopa of the mangrove crab *Metaplax distincta* H.Milne Edwards, 1852 (Brachyura: Sesarminae). *J Plankton Res.* 11:633–648.
- Le Vay L., Ut V.N., Walton M. 2007. Population ecology of the mud crab *Scylla paramamosain* (Estampador) in an estuarine mangrove system; a mark-recapture study. *Mar Biol.* 151:1127–1135.
- Lee S.H. 2022. Morphology of First Zoea Stage of *Sphaerozius nitidus* (Decapoda: Eriphioidea: Menippidae) Reared in the Laboratory Material. *Animal Systematics, Evolution and Diversity.* 38:83–90.
- Lewis L., Ayers J. 2014. Temperature preference and acclimation in the Jonah Crab, *Cancer borealis*. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology.* 455:7–13.
- Li J.-J., Shih H.-T., Ng P.K.L. 2019. Three New Species and Two New Records of *Parasesarma* De Man, 1895 (Crustacea: Brachyura: Sesarmidae) from Taiwan and the Philippines from Morphological and Molecular Evidence. *Zoological Studies.*:23.
- Liu H.-C., Jeng M.-S. 2007. Some Reproductive Aspects of *Gecarcoidea lalandii* (Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) in Taiwan. *Zoological Studies.*:8.
- Lucas J.S. 1980. Spider crabs of the family Hymenosomatidae (Crustacea; Brachyura) with particular reference to Australian species: Systematics and biology. *Rec. Aust. Mus.* 33:148–247.
- Lucas J.S. 1971. The larval stages of some Australian species of *Halicarcinus* (Crustacea, Brachyura, Hymenosomatidae). I. Morphology. *Bulletin of Marine Science.* 21:471-490.
- Lucas J.S. 1972. The larval stages of some Australian species of *Halicarcinus* (Crustacea, Brachyura, Hymenosomatidae). II. Physiology. *Bulletin of Marine Science.* 25:824-840.
- Madeira D., Narciso L., Cabral H.N., Diniz M.S., Vinagre C. 2012. Thermal tolerance of the crab *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*: intraspecific differences at a physiological (CTMax) and molecular level (Hsp70). *Cell Stress and Chaperones.* 17:707–716.
- Magalhaes C. 1996. Taxonomy of the Neotropical freshwater crab family Trichodactylidae III. The genera *Fredilocarcinus* and *Goyazana*. *Senckenbergiana biologica*:12.
- Magalhães C., Barbosa U.C., Py-Daniel V. 2006. Decapod crustaceans used as food by the Yanomami Indians of the Balawa-ú village, State of Amazonas, Brazil. *Acta Amaz.* 36:369–374.
- Maitland D.P. 1990. Aerial respiration in the semaphore crab, *Heloecius cordiformis*, with or without branchial water. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Physiology.* 95:267–274.
- Marijnissen S.A.E., Michel E., Daniels S.R., Erpenbeck D., Menken S.B.J., Schram F.R. 2006. Molecular evidence for recent divergence of Lake Tanganyika endemic crabs (Decapoda: Platythelphusidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution.* 40:628–634.
- Matsumasa M., Kikuchi S., Takeda S., Poovachiranon S., Yong H.-S., Murai M. 2001. Blood Osmoregulation and Ultrastructure of the Gas Windows ('Tympana') of Intertidal Ocy podoid Crabs: *Dotilla* vs. *Scopimera*. *Benthos Research.* 56:47–55.
- McGaw I.J. 2005. Burying behaviour of two sympatric crab species: *Cancer magister* and *Cancer productus*. *Sci. Mar.* 69:375–381.
- Melrose M.J. 1975. The Marine Fauna of New Zealand: Family Hymenosomatidae (Crustacea, Decapoda, Brachyura). :123.

- Miculka B. 2009. Burrowing Habits, Habitat Selections, and Behaviors of Four Common Dominican Land Crabs; *Guinotia dentata*, *Gecarcinus lateralis*, *Gecarcinus ruricola*, and *Cardisoma guanhumi*. :16.
- Molina Z.S., Neri J.B., Cañete R.M.P., Metillo E.B. 2020. Body Size, Habitat, and Diet of Freshwater Crabs *Isolapotamon mindanaoense* and *Sundathelphusa miguelito* (Crustacea: Brachyura) in the Municipality of Lake Sebu, South Cotabato, Philippines. *Science Diliman*:21.
- Morris S. 2002. The ecophysiology of air-breathing in crabs with special reference to *Gecarcoidea natalis*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part B: Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*. 131:559–570.
- Murai M., Henmi Y., Matsumasa M., Backwell P.R.Y., Takeshita F. 2022. Attraction waves of male fiddler crabs: A visual display designed for efficacy. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*. 546:151665.
- Naderloo R., Fatemi Y. 2015. New record of the rare alien grapsoid crab *Percnon affine* (H. Milne Edwards, 1853) (Crustacea, Decapoda, Grapsoidea, Plagusidae) from the northern Indian Ocean. *Mar. Biodivers. Rec.* 8:e92.
- Naderloo R., Türkay M. 2009. A new species of the genus *Nanosesarma* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Sesarmidae), and redescription of *Nanosesarma jousseaumei* (Nobili, 1906), including new records from the Persian Gulf. *Journal of Natural History*. 43:2911–2923.
- Naderloo R., Türkay M., Sari A. 2013. Intertidal habitats and decapod (Crustacea) diversity of Qeshm Island, a biodiversity hotspot within the Persian Gulf. *Mar Biodiv.* 43:445–462.
- Ng P.K.L., Dudgeon D. 1992. The Potmididae and Parathelphusidae (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) of Hong Kong. *Invertebrate Systematics*:28.
- Ng P.K.L. 1995. *Somanniathelphusa lacuvita*, a new ricefield crab from Tonle Sap, Cambodia. *Asian Journal of Tropical Biology*:6.
- Ng P.K.L., Manuel-Santos M.R. 2007. Establishment of the Vultocinidae, a new family for an unusual new genus and new species of Indo-West Pacific crab (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Goneplacoidea), with comments on the taxonomy of the Goneplacidae. *Zootaxa*. 1558:39–68.
- Ng P.K.L., Ng P.Y.C. 2021. Land crabs (Crustacea: Brachyura: Gecarcinidae) of Singapore. *Nature in Singapore*. 14:113.
- Niu J., Hu X.L., Ip J.C.H., Ma K.Y., Tang Y., Wang Y., Qin J., Qiu J.-W., Chan T.F., Chu K.H. 2020. Multi-omic approach provides insights into osmoregulation and osmoconformation of the crab *Scylla paramamosain*. *Sci Rep.* 10:21771.
- Novak M. 2004. Diurnal activity in a group of Gulf of Maine decapods. *Crustac.* 77:603–620.
- Nye P.A. 1974. Burrowing and burying by the crab *Macrophthalmus hirtipes*. *New Zealand Journal of Marine and Freshwater Research*. 8:243–254.
- de Oliveira Rocha C.A., de Lira J.J.P.R., de Lemos Santana J., Guimarães M.P., dos Santos Calado T.C. 2019. Biological aspects of the marine crab *Plagusia depressa* (Fabricius, 1775) on the northeast coast of Brazil. *Marine Biology Research*. 15:181–190.
- Padate V.P., Vijaylaxmi J., Maurya S., Rivonker C.U. 2015. Morphology and morphometrics of *Dotilla myctiroides* (Decapoda: Brachyura: Dotillidae) from an impacted beach of Goa along west coast of India. 57:7.
- Padghane S., Chavan S. Habitat preference and maintenance of freshwater crab *Barytelphusa cunicularis* in concrete tank culture model. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*:7.
- Paoli F., Wirkner C.S., Cannicci S. 2015. The branchiostegal lung of *Uca vocans* (Decapoda: Ocypodidae): Unreported complexity revealed by corrosion casting and MicroCT techniques. *Arthropod Structure & Development*. 44:622–629.
- Papadopoulos I., Newman B.K., Schoeman D.S., Wooldridge T.H. 2006. Influence of salinity and temperature on the larval development of the crown crab, *Hymenosoma orbiculare* (Crustacea: Brachyura: Hymenosomatidae). *African Journal of Aquatic Science*. 31:43–52.
- Pati S.K., Devi A.R.S. 2015. *Spiralothelphusa gibberosa*, a new freshwater crab (Brachyura: Gecarcinucidae) from Thrissur district, Kerala, India. *Zootaxa*. 3963:416.
- Pati S.K., Sharma R.M. 2014. Description of *Ghatiana*, a new genus of freshwater crab, with two new species and a new species of *Gubernatoriana* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura: Gecarcinucidae) from the Western Ghat Mountains, India. *Journal of Natural History*. 48:1279–1298.
- Paula J. 2004. Patterns of temporal occurrence of brachyuran crab larvae at Saco mangrove creek, Inhaca Island (South Mozambique): implications for flux and recruitment. *Journal of Plankton Research*. 26:1163–1174.
- Paula J., Hartnoll R.G. 1989. The larval and post larval development of *Percnon gibbesi* (Crustacea, Brachyura, Grapsidae) and the identity of the larval genus *Pluteocaris*. *Journal of Zoology*. 218:17–37.
- Peyrot-Clausade M. 1989. Crab cryptofauna (Brachyura and Anomura) of Tikehau, Tuamotu Archipelago, French Polynesia. *Coral Reefs*. 8:109–117.

- Pinder A.W., Smits A.W. 1993. The Burrow Microhabitat of the Land Crab *Cardisoma guanhumi*: Respiratory/Ionic Conditions and Physiological Responses of Crabs to Hypercapnia. *Physiological Zoology*. 66:216–236.
- Qhaji Y., van Vuuren B.J., Papadopoulos I., McQuaid C., Teske P. 2015. A comparison of genetic structure in two low-dispersal crabs from the Wild Coast, South Africa. *African Journal of Marine Science*. 37:345–351.
- Rasmuson L.K. 2013. The Biology, Ecology and Fishery of the Dungeness crab, *Cancer magister*. *Advances in Marine Biology*. Elsevier. p. 95–148.
- Rodríguez G., Rodríguez R. 1992. The freshwater crabs of America. Family Trichodactylidae and supplement to the family Pseudothelphusidae. Paris: Orstom.
- Rolier Lara L., Wehrtmann I.S., Magalhaes C., Mantelatto F.L. 2013. Species diversity and distribution of freshwater crabs (Decapoda: Pseudothelphusidae) inhabiting the basin of the Rio Grande de Terraba, Pacific slope of Costa Rica. *Iajar*. 41:685–695.
- Rosa L.C. da, Santos R.B. dos, Freire K.M.F. 2018. First record of the cliff crab *Plagusia depressa* (Fabricius, 1775) (Decapoda: Plagusiidae) from the coast of Sergipe, Brazil. *Nauplius*. 26:e2018030.
- Rosenberg M.S. 2020. A fresh look at the biodiversity lexicon for fiddler crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura: Ocypodidae). Part 2: Biogeography. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 40:364–383.
- Sastry A.N. 1977. The Larval Development of the Jonah Crab, *Cancer borealis* Stimpson, 1859, Under Laboratory Conditions (Decapoda Brachyura). *Crustac*. 32:290–303.
- Schlotterbeck R.E. 1976. The Larval Development of the Lined Shore Crab, *Pachygrapsus crassipes* Randall, 1840 (Decapoda Brachyura, Grapsidae) Reared in the Laboratory. *Crustac*. 30:184–200.
- Schubart C.D., Cuesta J.A., Felder D.L. 2002. Glyptograpsidae, A New Brachyuran Family From Central America: Larval And Adult Morphology, And A Molecular Phylogeny Of The Grapsoidea. *Journal Of Crustacean Biology*. 22:17.
- Senkman L.E., Negro C.L., Lopretto E.C., Collins P.A. 2015. Reproductive behaviour of three species of freshwater crabs of the family Trichodactylidae (Crustacea: Decapoda) including forced copulation by males. *Marine and Freshwater Behaviour and Physiology*. 48:77–88.
- Shih H.-T., Fang S.-H., Ng P.K.L. 2007. Phylogeny of the freshwater crab genus *Somanniathelphusa* Bott (Decapoda:Parathelphusidae) from Taiwan and the coastal regions of China, with notes on their biogeography. *Invert. Systematics*. 21:29.
- Shih H.-T., Hsu J.-W., Wong K.J.H., Ng N.K. 2019. Review of the mudflat varunid crab genus *Metaplox* (Crustacea, Brachyura, Varunidae) from East Asia and northern Vietnam. *ZK*. 877:1–29.
- Spencer A.M., Fielding A.H., Kamemoto F.I. 1979. The Relationship between Gill NaK-ATPase Activity and Osmoregulatory Capacity in Various Crabs. *Physiological Zoology*. 52:1–10.
- Stanton D.J., Leven M.R., Hui T.C.H. 2017. Distribution of *Cryptopotamon anacoluthon* (Kemp, 1918) (Crustacea: Brachyura: Potamidae), a freshwater crab endemic to Hong Kong. *J. Threat. Taxa*. 9:9786.
- Stanton J.L., Sulkin S.D. 1991. Nutritional requirements and starvation resistance in larvae of the brachyuran crabs *Sesarma cinereum* (Bose) and *S. reticulatum* (Say). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology*:14.
- Stutz A.M. 1978. Tidal and diurnal activity rhythms in the striped shore crab *Pachygrapsus crassipes*. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Cycle Research*. 9:41–48.
- Sudha K., Anilkumar G. 1996. Seasonal growth and reproduction in a highly fecund brachyuran crab, *Metopograpsus messor* (Forsk.) (Grapsidae). *Hydrobiologia*. 319:15–21.
- Sukmaningrum T., Adji B.K., Pratiwi E.M., Larasati B., Sayekti P.R., Maulana I., Eprilurahman R. 2018. Diversity of crabs in the intertidal zone at Sundak Beach, Gunungkidul, Indonesia. :020066.
- Sutton P.G. 2009. The occurrence of the freshwater crab *Potamon fluviatile* (Decapoda: Brachyura) in Corfu. *Mar. Biodivers. Rec*. 2:e58.
- Takeda M., Miyake S. 1969. Crabs from the East China Sea. II : Addition to Brachygnatha Brachyrhyncha. *Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University*. 15:449–468.
- Takeda S., Matsumasa M., Kikuchi S., Poovachiranon S., Murai M. 1996. Variation in the Branchial Formula of Semiterrestrial Crabs (Decapoda: Brachyura: Grapsidae and Ocypodidae) in Relation to Physiological Adaptations to the Environment. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 16:472.
- Takeda S., Murai M. 2004. Microhabitat Use by the Soldier Crab *Mictyris brevidactylus* (Brachyura: Mictyridae): Interchangeability of Surface and Subsurface Feeding through Burrow Structure Alteration. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 24:327–339.
- Thrupp T.J., Pope E.C., Whitten M.M.A., Bull J.C., Wootton E.C., Edwards M., Vogan C.L., Rowley A.F. 2015. Disease profiles of juvenile edible crabs (*Cancer pagurus* L.) differ at two geographically-close intertidal sites. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*. 128:1–5.

- Tiralongo F., Messina G., Lombardo B.M. 2021. Invasive Species Control: Predation on the Alien Crab *Percnon gibbesi* (H. Milne Edwards, 1853) (Malacostraca: Percnidae) by the Rock Goby, *Gobius paganellus* Linnaeus, 1758 (Actinopterygii: Gobiidae). *JMSE*. 9:393.
- Tomikawa N., Watanabe S. 1992. Reproductive Ecology of the Xanthid Crab *Eriphia smithii* Mcleay. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 12:57–67.
- Trivedi J.N., Gadhavi M.K., Vachhrajani K.D. 2012. Diversity and habitat preference of brachyuran crabs in Gulf of Kutch, Gujarat, India. :11.
- Tsai J.-R., Lin H.-C. 2012. A Shift to an Ion Regulatory Role by Gills of a Semi-Terrestrial Crab. *Zoological Studies*:13.
- Tseng K.-Y., Tsai J.-R., Lin H.-C. 2022. A Multi-Species Comparison and Evolutionary Perspectives on Ion Regulation in the Antennal Gland of Brachyurans. *Front. Physiol.* 13:902937.
- Vannini M., Chelazzi G., Gherardi F. 1989. Feeding habits of the pebble crab *Eriphia smithi* (Crustacea, Brachyura, Menippidae). *Marine Biology*. 100:249–252.
- Vannini M., Gherardi F. 1988. Studies on the pebble crab, *Eriphia smithi* MacLeay 1838 (Xanthoidea Menippidae): patterns of relative growth and population structure. *Tropical Zoology*. 1:203–216.
- Venkatachari S.A.T., Vasantha N. 1981. Salinity tolerance and osmoregulation in the freshwater crab, *Barytelphusa guerini* (Milne Edwards). *Hydrobiologia*. 77:133–138.
- Vermeiren P., Abrantes K., Sheaves M. 2015. Generalist and Specialist Feeding Crabs Maintain Discrete Trophic Niches Within and Among Estuarine Locations. *Estuaries and Coasts*. 38:2070–2082.
- Vijaylaxmi J., Can A.A., Rivonker C.U. 2020. Population biology of some species of crabs along Goa, west coast of India. 49:8.
- Wada K., Kuroda M., Kamada M. 2005. Factors Influencing Coexistence of Two Brachyuran Crabs, *Helice tridens* and *Parasesarma plicatum*, in an Estuarine Salt Marsh, Japan. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 25:146–153.
- Wahyudi A.J., Wada S., Aoki M., Hama T. 2015. *Gaetice depressus* (Crustacea, Varunidae): Species profile and its role in organic carbon and nitrogen flow. *Ocean Sci. J.* 50:389–401.
- Waiho K., Fazhan H., Quintio E.T., Baylon J.C., Fujaya Y., Azmie G., Wu Q., Shi X., Ikhwanuddin M., Ma H. 2018. Larval rearing of mud crab (*Scylla*): What lies ahead. *Aquaculture*. 493:37–50.
- Walker J.B., Rinehart S.A., White W.K., Grosholz E.D., Long J.D. 2021. Local and regional variation in effects of burrowing crabs on plant community structure. *Ecology*. 102.
- Walton M.E., Le Vay L., Truong L.M., Ut V.N. 2006. Significance of mangrove–mudflat boundaries as nursery grounds for the mud crab, *Scylla paramamosain*. *Mar Biol.* 149:1199–1207.
- Wang Z., Bai Y., Zhang D., Tang B. 2018a. Adaptive evolution of osmoregulatory-related genes provides insight into salinity adaptation in Chinese mitten crab, *Eriocheir sinensis*. *Genetica*. 146:303–311.
- Wang Z., Wang Z., Shi X., Wu Q., Tao Y., Guo H., Ji C., Bai Y. 2018b. Complete mitochondrial genome of *Parasesarma affine* (Brachyura: Sesarmidae): Gene rearrangements in Sesarmidae and phylogenetic analysis of the Brachyura. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 118:31–40.
- Warren J. 1990. Role of burrows as refuges from sub-tidal predators of temperate mangrove crabs. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 67:295–299.
- Wear R.G., Fielder D.R. 1985. The marine fauna of New Zealand: larvae of the Brachyura (Crustacea, Decapoda). Wellington: New Zealand Dept. of Scientific and Industrial Research.
- Wehrtmann I.S., Magalhães C., Hernáez P., Mantelatto F.L. 2010. Offspring production in three freshwater crab species (Brachyura: Pseudothelphusidae) from the Amazon region and Central America. *Zoologia (Curitiba, Impr.)*. 27:965–972.
- Wehrtmann I.S., Magalhães C., Orozco M.N. 2016. The primary freshwater crabs of Guatemala (Decapoda: Brachyura: Pseudothelphusidae), with comments on their conservation status. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*. 36:776–784.
- Weiss M., Thatje S., Heilmayer O., Anger K., Brey T., Keller M. 2009. Influence of temperature on the larval development of the edible crab, *Cancer pagurus*. *J. Mar. Biol. Ass.* 89:753–759.
- Wilson B.M., Pohle G.W. 2016. Northern range expansion of the American talon crab, *Euchiropsus americanus* A. Milne-Edwards, 1880 (Decapoda, Grapsoidea, Plagusidae), to the Bay of Fundy, Canada. *Crustac.* 89:163–173.
- Woll A. 2003. In situ observations of ovigerous *Cancer pagurus* Linnaeus, 1758 in Norwegian waters (Brachyura, Cancridae). *Crustac.* 76:469–478.
- Wong K.J.H., Tao L.S.R., Leung K.M.Y. 2021. Subtidal crabs of Hong Kong: Brachyura (Crustacea: Decapoda) from benthic trawl surveys conducted by the University of Hong Kong, 2012 to 2018. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*. 48:102013.

- Wortham J.L., Pascual S. 2017. Grooming behaviors and gill fouling in the commercially important blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*) and stone crab (*Menippe mercenaria*). *Nauplius*. 25.
- Yeo D.C.J., Cai Y., Ng P.K.L. 1999. The freshwater and terrestrial decapod crustacea of Pulau Tioman, Peninsular Malaysia. *Raffles Bulletin of Zoology*:48.
- Yeo D.C.J., Ng P.K.L., Cumberlidge N., Magalhães C., Daniels S.R., Campos M.R. 2008. Global diversity of crabs (Crustacea: Decapoda: Brachyura) in freshwater. *Hydrobiologia*. 595:275–286.
- Young A.M., Elliott J.A. 2020. Life History and Population Dynamics of Green Crabs (*Carcinus maenas*). *Fishes*. 5:44.
- Zalota A.K., Spiridonov V.A., Kolyuchkina G.A. 2016. In situ observations and census of invasive mud crab *Rhithropanopeus harrisi* (Crustacea: Decapoda: Panopeidae) applied in the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov. *Arthropoda Selecta*. 25:39062–0.
- Zenone A., Badalamenti F., Giacalone V.M., Musco L., Pipitone C., Vega Fernández T., D'Anna G. 2017. Substrate preference and settlement behaviour of the megalopa of the invasive crab *Percnon gibbesi* (Decapoda, Percnidae) in the Mediterranean Sea. *Helgol Mar Res*. 70:21.
- Zhang D., Liu J., Qi T., Ge B., Liu Q., Jiang S., Zhang H., Wang Z., Ding G., Tang B. 2018. Comparative transcriptome analysis of *Eriocheir japonica sinensis* response to environmental salinity. *PLoS ONE*. 13:e0203280.
- Zimmermann B.L., Aued A.W., Machado S., Manfio D., Scarton L.P., Santos S. 2009. Behavioral repertory of *Trichodactylus panoplus* (Crustacea: Trichodactylidae) under laboratory conditions. *Zoologia (Curitiba, Impr.)*. 26:5–11.

Fig. S3

0.02

Fig. S4

0.06

Fig. S5

0.03

Fig. S8

0.05

Fig. S9

0.04

Fig. S10

0.06

Fig. S13

A

B

Fig. S14

Fig. S15

346 298 250 201 145 100 56 0

OUT Hignidae_Higna_adactyla
 OUT Diogenidae_Clibanarius_virescens
 OUT Kiwaidae_Kiwa_hirsuta
 OUT Lithodiidae_Neolithodes_nipponensis
 OUT Muriidae_Muria_albipennis
 OUT Porcellanidae_Petrolisthes_japonicus
 Dynomenidae_Metadyonemene_tanensis
 Dynomenidae_Hirsutodyonemene_ursula
 Dynomenidae_Dyonemene_hispida
 Dynomenidae_Dyonemene_praedator
 Dromiidae_Sphaerodromia_sp
 Dromiidae_Lauridromia_deshanai
 Dromiidae_Conchoecetes_artificiosus
 Dromiidae_Lewindromia_undulata
 Dromiidae_Meridromia_antillensis
 Homolidae_Lamoha_murotoensis
 Homolidae_Lamoha_longirostris
 Homolidae_Seychellia_orientalis
 Homolidae_Paromolopsis_boasi
 Homolidae_Homologenus_malayensis
 Homolidae_Homologenus_rostratus
 Homolidae_Paromola_japonica
 Latreillidae_Epumula_phalangium
 Latreillidae_Latreilla_valida
 Latreillidae_Latreilla_elegans
 Raninidae_Ranina_ranina
 Raninidae_Raninoides_benedicti
 Lyreididae_Lyreidus_tridentatus
 Lyreididae_Lysirude_griffini
 Raninidae_Cosmonotus_grayii
 Raninidae_Ranina_muriei
 Cycloporippidae_Tymolus_brucei
 Cycloporippidae_Tymolus_japonicus
 Cycloporippidae_Corycodus_disjunctipes
 Cycloporippidae_Corycodus_sp
 Cymonomidae_Cymonomus_sp
 Cymonomidae_Cymonomus_diogenes
 Hymenosomatidae_Hymenosoma_orbiculare
 Hymenosomatidae_Neohymenophylax_bovis
 Hymenosomatidae_Amamus_parallelus
 Hymenosomatidae_Elamena_producta
 Hymenosomatidae_Halicarcinus_cookii
 Hymenosomatidae_Halicarcinus_innotatus
 Occkeridae_Seychellia_alkaui
 Potamonautidae_Platythelphusa_armata
 Potamonautidae_Potamonautes_perlatus
 Potamonautidae_Potamonautes_subukia
 Potamididae_Potamon_fluviatile
 Potamididae_Potamon_persicum
 Potamididae_Cryptopotamon_aenacoluthon
 Potamididae_Nanhaiopotamon_hongkongense
 Potamididae_Isolapotamon_griswoldi
 Potamididae_Potamon_tanensis
 Gecarcinucidae_Gubernatoriana_gubernatoris
 Gecarcinucidae_Barytelphusa_cunicularis
 Gecarcinucidae_Barytelphusa_sp
 Gecarcinucidae_Ceylonthelphusa_sp
 Gecarcinucidae_Spiralothelphusa_senex
 Gecarcinucidae_Somanniathelphusa_cf_zanklon
 Gecarcinucidae_Ceylonthelphusa_sp
 Gecarcinucidae_Syntripisa_flavichela
 Gecarcinucidae_Parathelphusa_pantherina
 Gecarcinucidae_Parathelphusa_pantherina_ourdata
 Glyptograpsidae_Glyptograpsus_jamaicensis
 Glyptograpsidae_Platychirograpsus_spectabilis
 Cycopidae_Cycopoe_ceratophthalmus
 Cycopidae_Cycopidae_sinesis
 Cycopidae_Austruca_lactea
 Cycopidae_Gelasmus_borealis
 Cycopidae_Parkoeropsia_lespases
 Xenopthalmidae_Xenopthalmus_pinnotheroides
 Pinnotheridae_Arcotheres_sp
 Pinnotheridae_Neopinnotheres_cf_affinis
 Pinnotheridae_Holothuriphilus_pacificus
 Pinnotheridae_Pinnaxodes_chilensis
 Pinnotheridae_Pinnaxa_cylindrica
 Pinnotheridae_Rathbunika_persiei
 Pinnotheridae_Scleroplax_schmitti
 Pinnotheridae_Scleroplax_tubicola
 Xenograpsidae_Xenograpsus_ngatama
 Xenograpsidae_Xenograpsus_testudinatus
 Cryptochiridae_Haplocarcinus_marsupialis
 Cryptochiridae_Parkoeropsia_lespases
 Cryptochiridae_Fungicola_fagei
 Percnidae_Percnon_planisimum
 Percnidae_Percnon_affine_ourdata
 Grapsidae_Pachygrapsus_marmoratus
 Grapsidae_Grapsus_albolineatus
 Grapsidae_Pachygrapsus_plicatus
 Grapsidae_Metopograpsus_frontalis
 Grapsidae_Metopograpsus_messor
 Grapsidae_Metopograpsus_quadridentatus
 Plagusidae_Davusia_glabra
 Plagusidae_Euchirograpsus_americanus
 Plagusidae_Mesograpsus_kingsleyi
 Plagusidae_Plagusia_squamosa
 Mictyridae_Mictyris_sp
 Mictyridae_Mictyris_longicarpus
 Mictyridae_Parkoeropsia_lespases
 Macrophthalmidae_Macrophthalmus_setosus
 Macrophthalmidae_Macrophthalmus_teleostephanus
 Macrophthalmidae_Parkoeropsia_lespases_ourdata
 Macrophthalmidae_Chaenostoma_boscii
 Macrophthalmidae_Macrophthalmus_definitus
 Varunidae_Metapilumnus_lespases
 Varunidae_Gaetice_depressus
 Varunidae_Cyclograpsus_cinereus
 Varunidae_Hemigrapsus_crenulatus
 Varunidae_Erochei_japonica
 Varunidae_Hemigrapsus_penicillatus
 Gecarcinidae_Cardisoma_japonica
 Gecarcinidae_Cardisoma_grassum
 Gecarcinidae_Cardisoma_guanhumii
 Gecarcinidae_Gecarcinus_lateralis
 Gecarcinidae_Gecarcinus_tanensis
 Gecarcinidae_Gecarcinidae_natalis
 Dotillidae_Dotilla_myctrioides
 Dotillidae_Dotilla_wichmani
 Dotillidae_Scopimera_hyempana
 Dotillidae_Scopimera_proxima
 Dotillidae_Scopimera_intermedia
 Dotillidae_Tmethypocelis_ceratophora
 Sesamidae_Armases_cinereum
 Sesamidae_Parasesarma_affine
 Sesamidae_Parasesarma_pictum
 Sesamidae_Nanosesarma_minutum
 Sesamidae_Parasesarma_eumolpe
 Sesamidae_Parasesarma_bidens
 Retroplumidae_Retropluma_denticulata
 Epioboceraidae_Epiobocera_gilmanii
 Epioboceraidae_Epiobocera_sinuatifrons
 Pseudohelphusidae_Potamonautes_ourdata
 Pseudohelphusidae_Raddaus_orestris
 Pseudohelphusidae_Psychophallus_montanus
 Pseudohelphusidae_Psychophallus_sp
 Orithyidae_Orithya_sinica
 Trichodactylidae_Trichodactylus_dentatus
 Trichodactylidae_Fredocarcinus_apyrati
 Trichodactylidae_Valdivia_serrata
 Belliidae_Acanthocyclus_albatrossis
 Belliidae_Acanthocyclus_hassleri
 Chasmocarcinidae_Mesophaedusa_yokoyai
 Chasmocarcinidae_Chasmocarcinus_chacei
 Chasmocarcinidae_Chasmocarcinus_mississippiensis
 Oregonidae_Hyas_araneus
 Oregonidae_Oregonia_gracilis
 Oregonidae_Chionoecetes_tanneri
 Majidae_Hyas_lyratus
 Majidae_Maja_brachydactyla
 Majidae_Maja_squinado
 Majidae_Schizophrys_aspera
 Inachidae_Corythynus_frisei
 Inachidae_Ericerodes_veteronis
 Inachoidae_Arachnopsis_filipes
 Inachoidae_Colodius_granicus
 Inachoididae_Aepinus_septemspinus
 Inachoididae_Anasimus_latus
 Inachoididae_Inachoides_laevis
 Majidae_Maiopsis_panamensis
 Epialtidae_Pugetia_nipponensis
 Epialtidae_Pugetia_sp
 Epialtidae_Rochinia_sp
 Epialtidae_Taliepus_dentatus
 Epialtidae_Pisoides_edwardsii
 Epialtidae_Litania_sp
 Epialtidae_Notolopas_mexicanus
 Epialtidae_Macroceoloma_camptocerum
 Epialtidae_Sternia_sp
 Epialtidae_Leptopisa_setirostris_ourdata=
 Epialtidae_Leptopisa_setirostris
 Epialtidae_Tarima_sp
 Epialtidae_Hyastenus_sp
 Epialtidae_Doclea_canalifera
 Epialtidae_Doclea_canalifera2
 Mithracidae_Telephysis_ourdata
 Mithracidae_Microphrys_branchialis
 Mithracidae_Pitho_aculeata
 Mithracidae_Mithraculus_coryphe
 Mithracidae_Mithraculus_forceps
 Mithracidae_Thee_erosa
 Mithracidae_Ala_connata
 Mithracidae_Mithrax_hispidus
 Pilumnoididae_Pilumnoides_nudifrons
 Pseudocarcinidae_Pseudocarcinus_gigas
 Dairidae_Daira_americanus
 Dairidae_Daira_perlata
 Menippidae_Menippe_lumphi
 Menippidae_Myomenippe_lomasinii
 Menippidae_Myomenippe_hardwickii
 Acidopsidae_Acidops_timbriatus
 Acidopsidae_Acidops_sp
 Pseudozoidae_Euryozius_camachoii
 Carpillidae_Carpilius_corallinus
 Carpillidae_Carpilius_convexus
 Carpillidae_Carpilius_maculatus
 Geryonidae_Raymanninus_schmitti
 Geryonidae_Chaceon_mediterraneus
 Geryonidae_Chaceon_sp
 Ovalipidae_Ovalipes_stephensoni
 Ovalipidae_Ovalipes_indescens
 Ovalipidae_Ovalipes_punctatus
 Portunidae_Portunus_pelagicus
 Portunidae_Portunus_sayi
 Portunidae_Scylla_paramamosain
 Portunidae_Charybdis_ferata
 Portunidae_Tharatta_pyrina
 Carcinidae_Parathelphusa_orientalis
 Carcinidae_Carcinus_maenas
 Carcinidae_Portunus_latipes
 Thuidae_Thia_societatisland2
 Polybiidae_Bathynectes_longispina
 Polybiidae_Liocarcinus_depurator
 Polybiidae_Necora_puber
 Dairiidae_Dairioides_kusei
 Parthenopidae_Parthenope_longimanus
 Parthenopidae_Rhinolambrus_sp
 Parthenopidae_Ochtholambrus_excavatus
 Parthenopidae_Cryptopodia_fornicata
 Parthenopidae_Leirolambrus_punctatissimus
 Aethridae_Hepatus_sphellicusland2
 Matutidae_Matuta_sp
 Matutidae_Ashotrei_lunaris
 Calappidae_Acanthocarpus_alexandri
 Calappidae_Mursia_sp1
 Calappidae_Mursia_sp2
 Calappidae_Cyclocheilus_granulosa
 Calappidae_Calappa_calappa
 Calappidae_Calappa_pilargius
 Cheryonidae_Telmessus_cheragonusland2
 Conystidae_Corystes_cassivelaunus
 Conystidae_Gomezia_bicornis
 Conystidae_Jonahs_disiectus
 Cancridae_Metacarcinus_magister
 Cancridae_Cancer_borealis
 Cancridae_Anatokios_japonicus
 Cancridae_Cancer_pagurus
 Ethusidae_Ethusina_abyssicola
 Ethusidae_Ethusina_sexdentata
 Ethusidae_Parathelphusa_orientalis
 Dorippidae_Dorippe_quadridens
 Dorippidae_Heikeopsis_japonica
 Leucosidae_Ebalia_tuberculosa
 Leucosidae_Praebellia_longidactyla
 Leucosidae_Pythia_carinata
 Leucosidae_Pythia_sp
 Leucosidae_Tokoyu_abyssus
 Iphiculiidae_Iphiculus_convexus
 Leucosidae_Arcania_cornuta
 Leucosidae_Randallia_bulligera
 Conleyidae_Conleyus_sp
 Progeryonidae_Rhadinoplax_microcephalus
 Bythograeidae_Ganadilus_pira
 Bythograeidae_Austinothelphusa_ourdata
 Bythograeidae_Austinothelphusa_sp1and2
 Trichopeltidae_Trichopeltation_nobile
 Vulfocidae_Vulfocnus_artificiosus
 Euryplacidae_Frevillea_barbata
 Euryplacidae_Eucrate_crenata
 Euryplacidae_Eucrate_blackock
 Euryplacidae_Eucrate_sp
 Mathildellidae_Mathildella_rubra
 Erpithidae_Erphya_scalinella
 Erpithidae_Erphya_smithi
 Erpithidae_Erphya_verrucosa
 Trapezidae_Philipicarcinus_oviformis
 Trapezidae_Trapezia_rufopunctata
 Trapezidae_Trapezia_digitalis
 Trapezidae_Trapezia_septata
 Trapezidae_Trapezia_tigrina
 Dacryoplumidae_Dacryoplummus_rathbunae
 Ozidae_Epixanthus_sp
 Ozidae_Epixanthus_fronalis
 Ozidae_Lydia_annulipes
 Ozidae_Ozium_rugulosus
 Pseudozoidae_Pseudozoides_caystrus
 Platyxanthidae_Platyxanthus_ourdata
 Tanaccheidae_Tanaccheles_bidentata
 Pilumnidae_Danielum_tbauchac
 Pilumnidae_Pilumnus_agassizii
 Pilumnidae_Pilumnus_dasyopodus
 Pilumnidae_Pilumnus_vesperillo
 Galenidae_Galena_bispinosa
 Pilumnidae_Heteropanope_glabra
 Pilumnidae_Pilumnus_longicornis
 Pilumnidae_Tarameclon_spirosum
 Hypothalassidae_Hypothalassia_armata
 Bythograeidae_Bythograea_laubieri
 Bythograeidae_Bythograea_micros
 Goneplacidae_Goneplax_surugensis
 Goneplacidae_Pycnoplax_surugensis
 Goneplacidae_Carcinoplax_purpurea
 Goneplacidae_Neoplatyx_reoculus
 Platyxanthidae_Danielethus_patagonicus
 Platyxanthidae_Homalaspis_pilana
 Platyxanthidae_Omarioninus_balboa
 Scalopidiidae_Scalopidia_spinosipes
 Pseudorhombidae_Pseudorhombia_quadridentata
 Pseudorhombidae_Trapezioplax_tridentata
 Pseudorhombidae_Pseudorhombia_lamellipes
 Pseudorhombidae_Micropanope_sculptipes
 Pseudorhombidae_Panoplax_depressa
 Pseudorhombidae_Nanoplax_xanthiformis
 Pseudorhombidae_Thalassoplax_angusta
 Panopeidae_Panopeus_herbstii
 Panopeidae_Euryplum_limosum
 Panopeidae_Malacoplax_californiensis
 Panopeidae_Hexapanopeus_angustifrons
 Panopeidae_Acatitlobolus_bermudensis
 Panopeidae_Glyptoplax_smithii
 Panopeidae_Rhithropanopeus_harrisii
 Panopeidae_Dyspanopeus_sayi
 Panopeidae_Neopanope_jackardii
 Xanthidae_Lybia_tessellata
 Xanthidae_Aliactaea_lithostrotia
 Xanthidae_Carpopeus_papulosus
 Xanthidae_Edwardsium_lolipes
 Xanthidae_Paraxanthus_barbigers
 Xanthidae_Catakepodius_floridanus
 Xanthidae_Xanthodus_ourdata
 Xanthidae_Xanthodus_sternbergiiand2
 Xanthidae_Williamsimpsonia_denticulatus
 Xanthidae_Xantho_pilipes
 Xanthidae_Palapeda_cf_nitida
 Xanthidae_Cyclodius_obscurus
 Xanthidae_Pilodius_arcuolatus
 Xanthidae_Xanthias_canaliculatus
 Xanthidae_Atergatis_floridus
 Xanthidae_Atergatis_inagerrimus
 Xanthidae_Actaea_bifrons
 Xanthidae_Paractaea_sp
 Xanthidae_Platyactaea_dovi
 Xanthidae_Demania_scaberrima
 Xanthidae_Actaeodes_cf_tomentosus
 Xanthidae_Novactaea_bella

Carboniferous Permian Triassic Jurassic Cretaceous Paleogene Ng.

Fig. S19

Fig. S20

Fig. S21

Simplified habitat:
 Marine Terrestrial Freshwater

Permian Triassic Jurassic Cretaceous Paleogene Ng.

Fig. S22

Direct (marine) path grade:
 0 1 2 3 4 5

Permian Triassic Jurassic Cretaceous Paleogene Ng.

Fig. S23

A

Grade:

B

Grade:

Fig. S24

Indirect (freshwater) path grade:

0	1	2	3	4	5
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Permian Triassic Jurassic Cretaceous Paleogene Ng.

Fig. S25

A

B

C

D

Fig. S26

A

B

C

D

